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Review Article

ANTIBIOTIC PRESCRIPTIONS FOR ACUTE RESPIRATORY TRACT INFECTIONS IN PRIMARY CARE, MEDICAL, SURGICAL AND PAEDIATRIC WARDS: A REVIEW 2020

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Abstract:

Background: Although most respiratory tract infections (RTIs) are due to viral infections, they cause the majority of antibiotic (Abx) prescriptions in primary care. This systematic review summarises the evidence on the effectiveness of interventions in primary care aiming to reduce Abx prescriptions in patients ≥ 13 years for acute RTI.

Methods: We searched the databases "MEDLINE/PubMed" and "Cochrane Library" for the period from January 1, 2005, to August 31, 2016, for randomised controlled trials (RCTs) in primary care aiming at the reduction of Abx prescriptions for patients suffering from RTI. Out of 690 search results, 67 publications were retrieved and 17 RCTs were included. We assumed an absolute change of 10% as minimal important change.

Results: Twelve out of 17 included RCTs showed statistically significant lower Abx prescription rates in the intervention groups, but only six of them reported a clinically relevant reduction according to our definition. Communication skills training (CST) and point-of-care testing (POCT) were the most effective interventions. Pre-intervention Abx prescription rates varied between 13.5% and 80% and observed reductions ranged from 1.5 to 23.3%. Studies with post-intervention rates lower than 20% had no significant effects. Post-intervention observation periods ranged from 2 weeks up to 3.5 years. The design of the trials was heterogeneous precluding calculation of pooled effect size. The reporting of many RCTs was poor.

Conclusions: CST and POCT alone or as adjunct can reduce antibiotic prescriptions for RTI. Eleven out of 17 trials were not successfully reducing Abx prescription rates according to our definition of minimal important change. However, five of them reported a statistically significant reduction. Trials with initially lower prescription rates were less likely to be successful. Future trials should investigate sustainability of intervention effects for a longer time period. The generalisability of findings was limited due to heterogeneous designs and outcome measures. Therefore, a consensus of designing and reporting of studies aiming at reducing antibiotic prescriptions is urgently needed to generate meaningful evidence.

Keywords: Acute respiratory tract infections, Antibiotics, Primary care

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INTRODUCTION:

Although most respiratory tract infections (RTIs) are due to viral infections, they cause the majority of antibiotic prescriptions in primary care [1]. Most patients suffering from RTI do not benefit from an antibiotic treatment since severity and duration of the disease are not relevantly altered. On the contrary, many patients experience side effects such as diarrhoea and rash [2]. Additionally, unnecessary antibiotic prescriptions contribute to increasing bacterial resistance to standard antibiotics [3].

Various interventions have been evaluated to reduce antibiotic prescribing for RTI, e.g. public campaigns, distribution of printed educational material or group education meetings [4–6]. A recent systematic review found moderate short-term effects on antibiotic prescribing of interventions facilitating shared decision-making [7]. Another global review summarised the effects of antimicrobial stewardship programs in ambulatory care including interventions for all infectious conditions and children. This review found low-strength evidence for interventions including provider and/or patient education, guidelines, delayed prescribing (DP) and computerised clinical decision support systems (CDSS) [8]. It is expected that within the next years, antibiotic stewardship programs will need to be established worldwide [9]. So far, there is still a discussion and uncertainty about which specific elements of interventions lead to high effectiveness and sustainability [10]. Therefore, this review aims to update and summarise current evidence of various interventions in primary care on reducing antibiotic prescription rates (Abx prescription rates) due to acute RTIs in patients ≥ 13 years.

METHODS:

This is a systematic review reported according to the PRISMA Statement [11]. This systematic review was not registered.

Search methods for identification of trials

The systematic literature search was carried out in MEDLINE/PubMed and the Cochrane Library using the following search terms:

((antibiotic*) AND (“respiratory tract infection” OR “respiratory tract infections” OR “respiratory infection”) AND (communication OR training OR “point of care test” OR “rapid strep test” OR “delayed prescribing” OR intervention* OR “electronic decision support” OR “clinical decision support system” OR “clinical decision support systems” OR “shared decision making”) AND (“primary care” OR “primary health care” OR “medical care”)) OR (“Anti-Bacterial Agents”[Mesh]) AND (“Respiratory Tract Infections”[Mesh]) AND (“Primary Health Care”[Mesh] OR “Physicians, Primary Care”[Mesh]))

Additionally, the bibliographies of the included trials were screened for relevant intervention trials. We could not search further databases like EMBASE due to limited access and lack of funding.

RESULTS:**Study selection**

We searched databases on the 31st of July in 2016 and identified 690 publications. Reviewers independently screened for potentially relevant publications and categorised 215 publications as potentially relevant. After removal of duplicates ($n = 84$), the remaining 151 titles and abstracts were screened for eligibility and discussed by the reviewers. Disagreements between reviewers were resolved by consensus. Major reasons for exclusion were different trial populations, e.g. including children, trials carried out in non-primary care settings and non-randomised study designs. We excluded 84 out of 151 publications. A total of 67 potentially relevant articles were fully screened for inclusion and exclusion criteria

All cluster-randomised trials performed cluster-adjusted data analyses. The number of participating physicians ranged from 6 to 573. Most trials were conducted in Europe [13, 14, 20–22, 27, 28, 31], six trials in North America [15, 23–25, 30, 32] and one in Asia [33]. One trial was a multinational project carried

out in six European countries (Belgium, Spain, Wales, England, Poland and the Netherlands) [26]. Published baseline data was available for seven trials [14, 20, 23, 26–29]. Eleven trials assessed the Abx prescription rate right after patients' initial consultation [13, 20, 22, 23, 26–31, 33].

Primary endpoints

Data on Abx prescription rates was collected directly by physicians [20, 21, 26, 27, 31], by pharmacists using faxed or mailed prescriptions [21, 32], by field researchers [33] or by electronic medical records [13, 15, 22–25, 28, 29]. Four trials used special documentation software [14, 23–25].

The time period for registration of Abx prescriptions ranged from right after the initial consultation up to 28 days after initial consultation.

Six trials assessed effectiveness of the intervention after a longer period of time, within 1 year [15, 29] or within 18 months after the intervention [30], after 1 year [13, 20] or after 3.5 years

Description of participating physicians

Ten trials recruited primary care physicians in private practices [13, 14, 20–22, 26–29, 32], and seven trials recruited physicians from primary care clinics [15, 23–25, 30, 31, 33].

Description of patient population

Patients ≥ 13 years with acute upper and lower RTIs were included. The average age of patients was similar across trials and ranged from 40 to 53 years. The number of registered consultations varied from 149 to 1,115,359 [28, 32].

Description of interventions

Multifaceted interventions

Twelve RCTs used multifaceted interventions [13, 14, 20–26, 28–30]. Multifaceted interventions contain two or more components and address the different aspects of inadequate antibiotic prescribing. Due to the multifaceted interventions of the included trials, some of them are discussed repeatedly in the following subsections. For example, the factorial study design of Cals et al. allows reporting of the effect of the CST or POCT alone or combined [22].

Intervention elements addressing physicians

Twelve trials used interventions that addressed physicians [13, 14, 20–24, 26, 28–30, 32]. Four different types of interventions were evaluated:

A “classic” knowledge transfer approach using interactive seminars [13, 14, 21] and distribution of printed teaching and information materials [21, 23] as well as feedback on individual Abx prescription rates [13, 14, 21, 22, 24, 29]. Themes discussed included diagnosis-making and therapy of RTIs in accordance with guidelines as well as the challenge of increasing bacterial resistance.

A CST dealing with perceived pressure to prescribe where physicians learnt how to communicate with patients about their expectations on antibiotic prescribing and how to respond to patients' concerns. In three trials, physicians were trained in seminars [20–22]. One trial provided an Internet-based CST [26].

Physicians were introduced to the concept of DP. This implies advising patients with low probability of bacterial RTI to use a prescription for antibiotics only in case symptoms do not resolve or get worse up to a pre-defined point in time. Cals et al. combined this strategy with C-reactive protein (CRP) POCT [30]. POCT are simple diagnostic tests and allow measuring CRP directly in the practice. CRP is an acute-phase protein with increasing plasma concentration during inflammatory processes. The measurement of CRP with a POCT has been proved accurate and can increase diagnostic certainty if combined with clinical examination—especially for identifying patients at high risk of pneumonia [35, 36]. Gjelstad et al. implemented additional software applications that asked physicians to specify whether the concept of DP was used and to document the number of days agreed to postpone antibiotic use [14]. Worrall et al. compared two DP procedures—one of them employing a ready-to-use prescription and the other applying a post-dated prescription usable only up to 48 h after initial consultation [32]. Gulliford implemented information about DP within a CDSS [28].

Electronic health records (EHR) asked physicians to justify their treatment decision if an antibiotic was ordered and provided alternative treatment interventions [29].

Intervention elements addressing patients

Five trials implemented interventions addressing patients [20, 23, 25, 28, 33]. Four trials used patient brochures with information about RTIs as adjunct [20, 23, 25, 28]. One trial used an additional waiting room poster addressing increasing bacterial resistance and prescribing pressure as one of the main reasons for inadequate prescribing [20]. Linder et al. and Gulliford et al. implemented documentation software with the possibility to print patient information leaflets [25,

28]. In the RCT of Linder et al., it remained unclear how many physicians used this possibility [25]. In the trial of Gulliford et al., the number of printed leaflets was low among the physicians with the highest utilisation of the CDSS (25 leaflets per 1000 consultations for RTI) [28]. In the trial of Hui Min Lee et al., patients in the IG were educated on the aetiology of upper RTIs by trained field researchers prior to the consultation [33].

Intervention elements addressing improved diagnosis-making

Twelve trials implemented interventions addressing diagnosis-making [13, 15, 22–31]. In one trial, the POCT was combined with a CST [22]. Another trial combined POCT with the strategy of DP [30]. Little et al. provided CRP-POCT training via the Internet [26]. Andreeva et al. used the CRP-POCT as a single intervention [27]. Bjerrum et al. employed a rapid antigen detection test for identifying group A streptococcal infections (RADT) in combination with feedback on personal prescribing rates [13]. Llor et al. used the RADT by itself [31]. The RADT is a fast pathogen identification test and can assist a physician in differentiating between a bacterial pharyngitis caused by group A streptococci or a viral infection. In combination with clinical scores such as the McIsaac score, it can raise diagnostic certainty and help to avoid unnecessary antibiotic prescriptions [37].

Six trials made use of CDSS [15, 23–25, 28, 29]. Linder et al. [24, 25] and McGinn et al. [15] provided assistance for estimating the likelihood of a bacterial RTI [24, 25] or a pneumonia/streptococcal pharyngitis [15]. Gulliford et al. provided evidence from research for antibiotic prescribing when a RTI was coded in an electronic medical record [28]. Andreeva et al. compared two different methods of diagnostic assistance: a computer-based system and a poster with a clinical algorithm [23]. Meeker et al. asked their participating physicians to justify their entered diagnosis and treatment [29].

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION:

CST and POCT alone or in combination have the potential to reduce antibiotic prescriptions for RTIs. Electronic decision support tools showed only mixed results. Eleven out of 17 trials were not successful in reducing Abx prescription rates according to our definition of minimal important change [13–40]. However, six of them reported a statistically significant reduction [13–15, 20, 28, 29]. Trials with low initial Abx prescription rates were less likely to be successful. Despite a number of noteworthy current studies, the generated evidence remains disappointingly limited. Only moderate evidence

which interventional strategies are successful and how these findings could be generalised beyond the actual setting and the observational period of the trial exist.

We conclude that there is a need to develop a consensus for designing and reporting of trials aiming to reduce inappropriate Abx prescriptions in the near future. It should address (among others) the measurement of pre-intervention prescribing rates, adjustment for seasonal and temporal trends, (minimal) follow-up time, data analysis and reporting.

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